

Scoring Rubric

Clarity: How understandable, readable, and unambiguous is the EUS?

1. very unclear, highly ambiguous or poorly written
2. somewhat unclear, several ambiguities or awkward phrasing
3. understandable overall, but with some ambiguity or readability issues
4. clear and easy to understand, with only minor wording issues
5. very clear, precise, and easy to understand, with no relevant ambiguity

Completeness: How complete is the EUS as an artifact?

Expected elements: title; description with role, goal, and benefit; work items/acceptance criteria.

1. major elements are missing
2. several expected elements are missing or underdeveloped
3. the main elements are present, but some are incomplete or weakly specified
4. almost all expected elements are present and reasonably specified
5. all expected elements are present and well specified

Actionability: To what extent can the EUS realistically guide implementation?

- cannot guide implementation, too abstract or unusable
- weak guidance, requires major interpretation before implementation
- provides some implementation guidance, but still needs refinement
- provides clear implementation guidance with minor gaps
- directly supports implementation with concrete and usable tasks

Testability: How concrete and verifiable are the work items/acceptance criteria?

- not testable, purely abstract or aspirational
- weakly testable, most items are vague or unverifiable
- partially testable, some items are concrete, others remain vague
- mostly testable, most items can be verified in practice
- clearly testable, all or nearly all items are concrete and verifiable

Faithfulness: How well does the EUS preserve the meaning of the original ethical requirement without adding unsupported constraints?

- seriously misrepresents the requirement or adds unsupported meaning
- partially misaligned, important aspects are distorted or unsupported additions are present
- generally aligned, but with some drift or minor unsupported additions
- closely aligned with the requirement, with only minor deviation
- fully faithful to the requirement; preserves its meaning without unsupported additions